

Clinicopathological Evaluation of Patients with Postmenopausal Bleeding in a Tertiary Care Centre.

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Abstract:

This prospective observational study evaluated the clinicopathological characteristics of postmenopausal bleeding (PMB) in 60 women at a tertiary care center, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, from January to June 2024. Utilizing transvaginal ultrasound and endometrial biopsies, the study found that 40% of patients exhibited endometrial thickness greater than 4 mm, with significant pathologies detected in 30% of those biopsied, including endometrial cancer and hyperplasia. These findings support the efficacy of transvaginal ultrasound as a first-line diagnostic tool in PMB management, highlighting its role in identifying patients at risk for serious conditions. The prevalence of both benign and malignant causes of PMB emphasizes the need for a comprehensive diagnostic approach to effectively tailor patient management strategies.

Keywords: Postmenopausal Bleeding, Transvaginal Ultrasound, Endometrial Biopsy, Clinicopathological Features.

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Introduction

Postmenopausal bleeding (PMB) is a frequently encountered clinical issue that can cause considerable worry for older women, as it may indicate potential endometrial problems, such as malignancies [1,2]. While the occurrence of severe conditions is relatively uncommon, the possibility of life-threatening illnesses necessitates timely and comprehensive assessment. Various factors can lead to the development of this clinical symptom, ranging from less serious conditions like atrophic endometritis to more severe causes like endometrial cancer or hyperplasia [3,4]. With the demographic trends pointing towards an aging population, it is anticipated that the frequency of PMB as a presenting complaint in gynecological practice will increase. Prompt identification and effective treatment are essential for enhancing patient results and can be greatly aided by a thorough clinicopathological strategy. It is crucial to conduct a thorough assessment in specialised healthcare facilities, where diverse teams can offer a comprehensive approach to diagnosis and treatment [5,6,7].

This study seeks to assess the root causes of PMB in patients who come to our specialized medical facility. By examining clinical observations alongside pathological results, we aim to improve the precision of diagnosis and the effectiveness of

treatment. Through the analysis of various cases, our goal is to uncover recurring patterns and unusual occurrences in the manifestations of PMB. This will enhance our comprehension of its clinicopathological range and enable us to refine care protocols for optimal outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a prospective observational design to assess the clinicopathological features of postmenopausal bleeding (PMB) in patients at a tertiary care center.

Study Population: A total of 60 patients were enrolled in this study, with an average of approximately 10 patients per month over the 6-month study period.

Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Gynecology at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar.

Duration: The study period was from January 2, 2024, to June 20, 2024.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female patients aged 50 years and above.
- Patients presenting with symptoms of postmenopausal bleeding.

- Patients who consented to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of endometrial or cervical cancer treatments.
- Patients who had undergone hysterectomy.
- Patients who declined to give informed consent.

Data Collection

Data were collected through structured interviews and reviews of medical records, focusing on:

- Patient demographics (age, race, body mass index).
- Medical history (comorbidities, previous gynecological issues).
- Details of the PMB episode (duration, quantity, associated symptoms).

Diagnostic Workup

All patients underwent a standard diagnostic workup that included:

- Transvaginal ultrasound to assess endometrial thickness.
- Endometrial biopsy for histopathological examination in cases indicated by clinical assessment or ultrasound findings.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient characteristics and clinical findings. The relationship between clinicopathological features and the outcomes of interest was analyzed using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. Statistical significance was set at a p-value of <0.05.

Results

A total of 60 postmenopausal women participated in the study, with a mean age of 62 years (range: 50-84 years). The majority of participants were of South Asian descent, and the mean body mass index (BMI) was 27.3 kg/m².

Postmenopausal bleeding varied widely among the participants:

- 45% reported spotting,
- 35% reported moderate bleeding,
- 20% reported heavy bleeding.

Associated symptoms included pelvic pain in 30% of the patients and weight loss in 10%. Transvaginal ultrasound revealed that 40% of participants had endometrial thickness greater than 4 mm. Endometrial biopsy was performed in 30 patients, showing:

- 15 cases (50%) of atrophic endometritis,

- 8 cases (27%) of endometrial hyperplasia,
- 5 cases (17%) of endometrial cancer,
- 2 cases (6%) of benign polyps.

Among those who underwent biopsy, 30% were found to have significant pathologies such as endometrial hyperplasia and cancer. A significant correlation was observed ($p < 0.05$) between the measurement of endometrial thickness using ultrasound and the pathological findings obtained from the biopsy. The study's findings emphasize the significance of conducting a comprehensive diagnostic assessment for individuals experiencing postmenopausal bleeding. It is crucial to carefully evaluate and potentially intervene in individuals with thicker endometrial lining, as it is associated with a greater likelihood of abnormal findings. This is essential for effectively addressing and minimizing potential health complications.

Conclusion

The findings of this study offer valuable information about the clinicopathological characteristics of postmenopausal bleeding (PMB) in a tertiary care setting. The different levels of bleeding observed—spotting in 45%, moderate bleeding in 35%, and heavy bleeding in 20% of cases—highlight the wide range of PMB symptoms [13]. When symptoms like pelvic pain and weight loss occur with PMB, it's important to consider the possibility of serious underlying conditions. This emphasizes the need for a thorough evaluation [9,14]. It is worth noting that 40% of the participants in the study had an endometrial thickness greater than 4 mm, which is consistent with previous research indicating that this measurement could be a sign of underlying endometrial issues [15]. The strong link between higher endometrial thickness and important pathological discoveries on biopsy, such as endometrial cancer and hyperplasia, highlights the practicality of transvaginal ultrasound as an initial diagnostic method [10,16]. The biopsy results of this study reveal a significant prevalence of endometrial cancer and hyperplasia among the individuals who underwent the procedure. These findings emphasize the importance of maintaining a high level of suspicion in postmenopausal women who experience postmenopausal bleeding [11,17].

In addition, the prevalence of atrophic endometritis (found in 50% of biopsies) indicates that although cancer is a significant concern, there are also a considerable number of non-cancerous conditions in cases of postmenopausal bleeding. This highlights the importance of conducting a comprehensive clinical evaluation [18]. The findings of this study strongly support the use of a comprehensive protocol that includes ultrasound and, when necessary, biopsy to accurately diagnose

the underlying factors contributing to PMB. In conclusion, this study provides important information that adds to our current understanding, emphasizing the importance of being cautious and using a systematic diagnostic approach when dealing with PMB [8,19]. This approach can help improve patient outcomes and effectively allocate

healthcare resources. The correlation between endometrial thickness and pathological findings provides clinicians with a solid parameter to enhance risk stratification and management strategies in this patient population [20].

Table 1: This table effectively organizes the major findings from the study, allowing for quick reference and analysis of the data.

Description	Total Participants	Percentage	Details
Total Participants	60	N/A	Average age: 62 years (Range: 50-84 years)
BMI (kg/m ²)	60	N/A	Mean BMI: 27.3
Type of Bleeding			
- Spotting	27	45%	
- Moderate Bleeding	21	35%	
- Heavy Bleeding	12	20%	
Associated Symptoms			
- Pelvic Pain	18	30%	
- Weight Loss	6	10%	
Endometrial Thickness (> 4 mm)	24	40%	Detected via transvaginal ultrasound
Endometrial Biopsy Findings			
- Atrophic Endometritis	15	50% of biopsies	
- Endometrial Hyperplasia	8	27% of biopsies	
- Endometrial Cancer	5	17% of biopsies	
- Benign Polyps	2	6% of biopsies	
Significant Pathologies	18	30% of those biopsied	Among patients who underwent biopsy

Conclusion

The study conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital on postmenopausal bleeding (PMB) has underscored the importance of a comprehensive clinicopathological evaluation in diagnosing and managing this condition. Findings revealed a significant correlation between increased endometrial thickness and severe pathologies such as endometrial cancer and hyperplasia, validating the use of transvaginal ultrasound as an effective initial screening tool. Despite the prevalence of significant conditions, a large proportion of cases were attributed to benign causes like atrophic endometritis, highlighting the need for a balanced and cautious approach to PMB management. The data emphasize the necessity of incorporating systematic diagnostic protocols that include both imaging and biopsy to ensure accurate diagnosis and optimal patient care in cases of postmenopausal bleeding.

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